

TRANSACTIONAL COMMUNICATION SKILLS OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS: CRAFTING INTERVENTION PROGRAM FOR ENHANCEMENT

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Transactional Communication Skills of Senior High School Students: Crafting Intervention Program for Enhancement

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Abstract

This qualitative study sought to identify current issues and challenges encountered by SHS students in their transactional communication skills and propose the needed intervention program to address the identified problems. The study employed a descriptive-phenomenological approach which aimed to understand the experiences of SHS students when it comes to their transactional communication skills. In-depth interviews were used to gather the grade 12 SHS students and teachers' experiences and observations in transactional communication. Results showed that SHS students encountered issues and challenges were (1) communication anxiety, (2) low level of confidence, (3) vernacular dependence, (4) limited grammar and vocabulary, and (5) pronunciation struggles. In addition, coping mechanisms employed by the students were (1) conversation termination, (2) self-regulation, (3) observational coping and assistance finding, and (4) technology assistance. All these provide empirical evidence for the need to have and implement an intervention program that would address the identified issues and challenges. Furthermore, the use and integration of technology in the instruction and intervention program provide meaningful learning. Future studies should identify the effectiveness and long-term effect of the interventions provided to the students, especially with technology integration in their transactional communication skills. Moreover, it is hoped that the proposed intervention plan will be materialized to address SHS students' encountered issues and challenges.

Keywords: *transactional communication skills, coping mechanisms, intervention program*

Introduction

Efficient, enjoyable, and smooth communication is achieved through effective transactional communication. Having excellent speaking and listening skills is crucial, which facilitates mutual comprehension and efficient communication in a variety of contexts, both personally and professionally. Yet, speaking is one of the most vital aspects of communication, but rarely practiced (Al Hosni, 2014). Although English is already utilized in the Philippine educational system as a subject and a medium of instruction, Filipino students still struggle to learn it, particularly when it comes to oral proficiency, which could have an impact on their performance in advanced coursework and even when they apply for jobs (Pangket, 2019).

Globally, through the passage of time, oral communication challenges persist within educational institutions. These issues may stem from various sources, including student-related factors, teacher-related factors, and, notably, systemic shortcomings within the educational framework. Several standardized tests are conducted to check student's speaking skills. In the Education Ministry of Japan's April 2019 nationwide achievement test, students averaged 30.8% in speaking, indicating a lack of proficiency in oral communication—a problem that has long plagued English instruction. In the meantime, the K–12 curriculum has been implemented in the Philippines in response to the need for well-rounded individuals, to provide students with the skills and knowledge necessary to meet the demands of the twenty-first century (DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2019). Furthermore, it is the goal of the K–12 Senior High School Core Curriculum (EN11/12OC-IIab-21) to produce senior high school graduates who possess the ability to communicate effectively, particularly transactional communication.

In the national context however, Grade 11 students at Polillo National High School in Quezon showed signs of extreme anxiety and fear when speaking and responding during various classroom activities, according to Azagra's (2017) study. Senobio (2015) has also highlighted the considerable difficulty Filipino learners face in both learning and teaching English. A significant contributing factor to this challenge is the negative perception students hold regarding speaking the language. Students often perceive speaking English as unpatriotic, which exacerbates the issue. Additionally, these problems were intensified especially with the adoption of modular distance learning (MDL) in schools located in rural areas during the pandemic in which a study conducted by Dargo and Dimas (2021) revealed that there was a significant decrease on students' academic performance after the adoption of MDL. This is alarming since the locale of the study adopted MDL for 2 consecutive school years. Furthermore, in a more recent finding by the Commission of Human Rights (CHR) last year 2023, it was revealed that SHS graduates of the pandemic generation are finding it more difficult to land jobs as many of them lack “soft skills” which include communication.

These issues with oral communication skills are presently evident in students' lack of desire to learn how to communicate in English and their nervousness when teachers ask questions, or even when they have to act out certain scenarios (such as inviting friends to a birthday party, ordering takeout online, or giving directions) that call for English-language responses, are consistently visible in regular classroom activities. Oftentimes, students ask the teachers if they could deliver their answers or lines in vernacular or mixed. Still, even if they are already delivering their answer using their dialect, the stuttering, fluctuation of voice, shaky hands, poor eye contact, low voice, the use of vernacular expressions like “kanang”, “kuan”, “unsa gani na ha?”, and the students' refusal to answer even a very

simple question are observed.

Locally, Lupiba (2017) discovered that grade 10 learning materials' communicative activities helped students improve their transactional and conversational communication skills. However, the outcomes do not match with the SHS students' present transactional communication abilities. Thus, the materials used in their previous year do not guarantee that they acquire the skills. In the grading system, 50% of the grades come from performance tasks, which commonly involve speaking. This situation has greatly affected their overall English performance.

Given all the aforementioned concerns about oral proficiency in a second language, it is critical to investigate the state of SHS students' transactional communication skills and implement an appropriate and trustworthy intervention program to address the difficulties and problems that students are having with these skills. Their ability to communicate verbally can strengthen and develop their transactional tasks that are crucial in real-world situations.

Research Questions

This study aimed to explore the transactional communication skills of Grade 12 senior high school students at one of the senior high schools located in Davao City, identify areas for improvement, and inform the development of effective interventions. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What issues and challenges do senior high school students experience when it comes to their transactional communication skills as confirmed by the teachers?
2. What are the coping mechanisms that students employ when they experience issues and challenges in their transactional communication skills?
3. Based on the results, what interventions could be proposed to address the identified issues and challenges that senior high school students encounter when it comes to their transactional communication skills?

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive-phenomenological approach. A qualitative approach enabled a researcher to delve into the behavior, perspectives, experiences, and emotions of an individual, necessitating a profound comprehension of these aspects (Burns and Grove, 2003; Holloway and Wheeler, 2002). The phenomenological approach's aim was to understand the nature of things based on the experiences of people (Gill, 2020). It included in-depth interviews and observations that gained insights into students' experiences and performances.

Descriptive-phenomenological approach is the best approach to be used in the study since it sought to explore and identify the issues and challenges of senior high school students when it comes to their transactional communication skills as well as the coping mechanisms they employ when they encounter issues and challenges. To extract the needed data, in depth interviews are needed to understand the respondents' perspectives and experiences on the phenomena being investigated which is the low performance in senior high school students' transactional communication skills, hence the qualitative phenomenological approach was used.

Respondents

As shown in Table 1, the respondents for the study were Grade 12 senior high school students at one of the senior high schools located in Davao City, selected through a purposive sampling technique. A total of 5 students and 5 teachers were selected as respondents. The students were referred to as "respondents" in the study since they responded to assessment tools and participated in interviews, The teachers were referred to as "informants" as they have shared their observations of the students inside the school in which they teach and at the same time where students are studying. Informants are individuals that share knowledge with a researcher from an insider's perspective.

Table 1. *Grade 12 Student Respondents*

<i>Grade 12 SHS Student Respondents</i>	<i>Specialization</i>
Student 1	Food Processing NC II
Student 2	Food Processing NC II
Student 3	Animal Production NC II
Student 4	Organic Agri NC II
Student 5	Animal Production NC II

Table 2. *Grade 12 SHS Teacher Informants*

<i>Grade 12 SHS Teacher Informants</i>	<i>Years in Teaching</i>
Teacher 1	6 years
Teacher 2	10 years
Teacher 3	7 years
Teacher 4	10 years
Teacher 5	12 years

The respondents were identified purposively, regardless of their gender and socio-economic background. However, the ages of the students were 16–19 years old. The teacher informants were identified regardless of their age, and gender, but were based on the grade level that they handled and the number of years that they are teaching that is a minimum of 5 years. The researcher ensured that these educators worked with 12th graders for them to provide insightful commentary and validate the experiences of the study's primary respondents.

Specialization: The Technical-Vocational-Livelihood Track (TVL) at the locale of the study offered specializations, including Food Processing NC II, Animal Production NC II, and Organic Agriculture NC II. The selection process was done to ensure that the sample represented the range of educational experiences and difficulties that students encountered while developing their transactional communication skills.

The sources of data for the study were derived from researcher made guide questionnaire to identify the challenges and issues in the transactional skills of senior high school students which served as the key informant interview questionnaire with a subset of the students and teachers, serving as a source of qualitative data that offered insights into their experiences, challenges, and perceptions related to the development of their transactional skills.

The study was conducted at one of the senior high schools in Davao City. The locale was chosen not only for its geographical location but also due to the unique characteristics of the school and its student population in relation to the research variables. The diversity in the school an ideal setting to examine the transactional skills of senior high school students and identify the factors that contribute to their development. Moreover, the school's commitment to enhancing students' communication skills aligned with the goals of the study, making it a suitable locale for the research. In addition to the school's demographic and educational context, the researcher's familiarity with the locale and access to resources and support from the school administration further contributed to the decision to conduct the study at the said school. Moreover, the researcher aimed to generate insights and recommendations as well as craft an intervention program that could be applied and used not only to the specific context of the school but also to other senior high schools with similar characteristics, challenges, and goals related to the development of students' transactional skills.

Instrument

This study employed in-depth interviews as research instruments to gather data on the transactional skills of senior high school students. Each instrument was described in detail below, including the variables it intended to measure and the validity and reliability measures taken.

The researcher developed the interview questions with the intention of better understanding the problems and difficulties senior high school students faced with their transactional communication abilities. The instrument underwent 3 stages of revision before it was used in the interview proper. The first revision was after the expert checking of the researcher's adviser; the second was after the validation process, which included the expert corrections of one master teacher and two university experts; and the third was after the pilot test, a test of consistency of measurement in which it was defined as a term for rater consistency, referring to the extent to which raters can consistently discern between different items on a measurement scale (Shweta et al., 2015). Three language experts suggested some revisions to some of the questions in the instrument that led to the final instrument used in this study (Appendices D). The final instrument used in this study was divided into two parts. First part are questions for the student respondents which composed of 10 interview questions, 5 questions to answer statement of the problem 1 and another 5 questions to answer for statement of the problem number 2. Second part was questions for the senior high school teachers which composed of 10 questions, 5 to answer statement of the problem 1 and another 5 questions to answer statement of the problem number 2.

In-depth Interviews: Semi-structured interviews were conducted by the researcher with a subset of students to gather qualitative data on their experiences, challenges, and perceptions related to the development of their transactional skills. The interview guide was developed by the researcher based on relevant literature and expert input. The guide was designed to ensure that the questions were clear, unbiased, and focused on the variables of interest. Prior to data collection, the interview guide was first validated by 3 experts from the field second, after the validation, it was pilot tested with the same population and third, results of the pilot test were subjected for interrater assessment which ended with the use of the final interview questionnaire.

By employing the research instrument, the study aimed to gather comprehensive and reliable data to answer the research questions and address the statement of the problem. The conducted interviews with both students and their teachers also ensured the triangulation of data, which enhanced the validity and reliability of the findings.

Data Analysis

The data analysis for this study involved a qualitative approach to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the transactional skills of senior high school students. The following statistical treatments and data analysis techniques were employed:

Qualitative data analysis: The qualitative data gathered from in-depth interviews and structured observations were analyzed using Colaizzi's thematic analysis. This involved identifying, coding, and categorizing themes and patterns within the data, which helped to explore students' experiences, challenges, and perceptions related to their transactional skills.

Based on the data analysis techniques, this study aimed to provide a comprehensive and rigorous understanding of the transactional skills of senior high school students.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher recognized the importance of adhering to ethical principles in conducting the study to ensure the protection of human rights, maintain the integrity of the research process, and minimize any potential harm to the respondents and others involved. The following ethical considerations were addressed:

Informed consent. Prior to data collection, the researcher obtained informed consent from the respondents and ensured that they understood the purpose of the study, the voluntary nature of their participation, the procedures involved, and any potential risks and benefits.

Privacy and confidentiality. The researcher ensured that the respondents' privacy was protected by collecting data anonymously without obtaining any personally identifiable information. By safely keeping data and disclosing research findings in an aggregate form without identifying specific participants, confidentiality was upheld throughout the whole investigation.

Respect for human rights. The researcher was sensitive to cultural, social, and individual differences among the respondents and treated them with respect and dignity. The researcher avoided any discriminatory comments, irrelevant gestures, or biases that might harm the respondents or compromise the validity of the study.

Intellectual property rights. The researcher acknowledged the contributions of previous researchers and authors by properly citing their work in the literature review and adhering to copyright laws. The researcher also ensured that the developed intervention program respected the intellectual property rights of others and was created in compliance with relevant guidelines.

Minimizing harm to health, safety, and property. The researcher took all necessary precautions to minimize any risks to the respondents' health and safety during the data collection process, including adhering to proper safety protocols and ensuring a comfortable environment for the respondents. The researcher also minimized any potential damage to property by conducting the study responsibly and carefully.

Institutional review board approval. Approval from a pertinent institutional review panel was sought by the researcher to guarantee that the study followed ethical norms and procedures. The methodology and research design considered any suggestions made.

Addressing these ethical considerations, the researcher ensured that the study was conducted responsibly, respectfully protected the rights and well-being of the respondents, and contributed to the advancement of knowledge in the field of education.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the study's results and subsequent discussions, adopted Colaizzi's thematic analysis which served as a methodological approach to unravel the intricate narratives and patterns embedded within the interview transcripts. The presentation proceeds in this sequence: (a) issues and challenges encountered by senior high school students in their transactional communication skills, (b) coping mechanisms employed, (c) proposed intervention program to address identified issues and challenges in senior high school students' transactional communication skills.

Issues and Challenges Encountered by Senior High School Students in their Transactional Communication Skills

This section examined the issues and challenges Grade 12 senior high school students encountered regarding their transactional communication skills. The data was gathered by adopting Colaizzi's thematic analysis which served as a methodological approach to unravel the intricate narratives and patterns embedded within the interview transcripts.

Issues Encountered by Senior High School Students in their Transactional Communication Skills

An issue in the context of academics, is a specific topic, problem, or question that requires discussion, investigation, and intervention. Appropriate methodologies and theoretical frameworks should be used for it to be examined or systematically explored. Generally, there was an existence of an issue if certain policies and standards were not being achieved or followed affecting the overall productivity or expected output in various contexts. The results of this study revealed that communication anxiety was experienced by most of the learners especially when they communicate with unfamiliar people, with their classmates and teachers. They felt afraid and anxious every time they were engaged in transactional communication situations. Low confidence levels were also emphasized where students had difficulty in expressing their ideas because they were afraid to commit mistakes and too shy or afraid that they get judged by others. Teachers also observed the low confidence levels of students characterized by them being reluctant and shy whenever engaged in transactional communication situations. Additionally, vernacular use was also found to be an issue where students relied on emphasizing their message or thoughts in their vernacular language in cases they encounter difficulties in thoroughly expressing it in the English language.

Communication Anxiety. Communication apprehension is defined as "an individual's level of fear or anxiety associated with real or anticipated communication with another person or persons." This fear stems from the expected or perceived judgment from the

audience, as well as from the communicators themselves. It does not necessarily occur only on stage in front of a large audience; it can also arise during communication in smaller groups or one-on-one interactions (McCroskey, 1977 as cited on Lindberg, 2022). Senior high school students mostly experienced the feeling of being uncomfortable when encountering transactional communication situations especially when communicating with unfamiliar individuals. The result of this study paralleled the findings of Al Hosni (2014), where communicative difficulties were identified, such as inhibition, which was evident in this study in terms of social anxiety. Students expressed feelings of nervousness and struggled to express themselves fluently, particularly when communicating with unfamiliar individuals. Students' anxiety was further highlighted by their feelings of shyness, especially when interacting with unfamiliar individuals or in unfamiliar situations. When prompted to use English for transactional communication, students often experience discomfort due to a lack of practice in this skill outside of the classroom. The following excerpts from the senior high school students proved the existence of this situation:

"But if I'm with a stranger or I don't know the person I'm talking to, I might feel shy or I might not be able to express my ideas." (Student 1)

"Sometimes I'm nervous because I'm not used to speaking in English." (Student 2)

"but my experience has some initial comprehension in unfamiliar settings." (Student 3)

"Anxious, nervous because it's scary to make mistakes in what I'm saying." (Student 4)

"Yes Sir. Most of the time, especially if there is a presentation, especially if we are required to use the English language to present." (Student 5)

According to Barnlund's Transactional Communication Model, transactional communication is an exchange of information between sender and receiver and vice-versa in which communicators manipulated the information being sent and received. However, this communication anxiety issue hampered the essence of transactional communication. Some students expressed their best efforts to communicate effectively in these situations. Students 5 and 1 shared:

"Actually Sir, yes there are times. I encountered it with my friends, my friends in a city. It is common for them to use English, especially my cousins. So, I was also encouraged to use the language. So, that's why if we are together, I can also improve my English communication towards them." (Student 5)

"In public places, it also depends on the language of the stranger. If they use Tagalog, I can talk to them in Tagalog or Bisaya. If it's English, I can talk to them in Bisaya. If it's English, I can talk to them in Bisaya. It's like a mix of Tagalog and English. Sometimes, it's just a gesture. It's just a gesture." (Student 1)

The findings based on the observations of the senior high school teachers intensified the existence of the issues experienced by their students based on their statements. The statement of Teacher 1 highlighted that when required to use the English language in expressing their feelings and ideas, students could not fully and properly express it because of discomfort. This problem was further supported by observation from Teachers 2-5 who said:

"I observe that if there are students who feel uncomfortable communicating with their peers, they don't participate." (Teacher 1)

"The word stress is too heavy. Like, uncomfortable. They also worry if they are being understood or not." (Teacher 2)

"Students are really stressed if they are tasked to answer in English." (Teacher 3)

"I think it's somehow a feeling of worry because the students should understand the concept presented." (Teacher 4)

"Some of the students are worried because if they cannot understand or express their ideas, then that could be part of the grading." (Teacher 5)

This was not only evident inside the school communication situations but also outside the school when students encountered scenarios in which they needed to communicate with unfamiliar individuals. This identified problem of being shy and uncomfortable when communicating in the English language was also identified as the same factor that affected students' performance in communication (Tuan and Mai, 2015; Al Hosni, 2014). Additionally, when students were unable to express their feelings and thoughts in the English language, they resorted to using their vernacular language. This was evident in the statement of Teacher 1 who observed that when struggling with English, students reverted to their native language to express ideas, showing adaptability. Teacher 1 said:

"They're trying their best to express it somehow like in Filipino or in Bisaya" (Teacher 1)

Low Level of Confidence. The inability to communicate transactionally in social contexts was further influenced by students who were observed to have low confidence levels. Senior high school students felt that they were not fluent and they did not have the communicative skills needed to communicate properly. This situation was expressed from their responses:

"Sometimes, I'm not confident to chat with the teachers, especially English teachers like you, sir." (Student 1)

“I am not confident every time I do public speaking using the English language because I might get judged. So, I’m nervous.” (Student 2)

“I’m not a better communicator because I can’t deliver it in a way that he can understand.”(Student 3)

“Maybe if in terms of academics and I really have no idea what the topic or idea is, so I’m not confident to talk in English.” (Student 4)

“Yes Sir, like this situation, Ma’am interviewed me for her study. So, she interviewed us. I was nervous because Ma’am told us to use English through a speaking interview.”(Student 5)

Interviews with their teachers confirmed that the majority of Grade 12 senior high school students lacked confidence or exhibited low confidence. Teachers were asked to provide a scale to describe students' confidence levels in their transactional communication skills based on their observations. Teachers 1, 2, and 4 confirmed this claim and stated:

“Good afternoon, for me some of the students are not confident, some are feeling shall we say insecure when it comes to English communication, and some also are capable in doing so.” (Teacher 1)

“As for their confidence level, I can say that most of them are in the poor level, low level. Though there are still others who belong to the high level, mostly, most of the students fall under the low level of their confidence. (Teacher 2)

“Their confidence level is really low, maybe it's at 5. That's based on my observation.”(Teacher 3)

“75 percent to 80 percent because usually, most of the students have a hard time in communicating, especially when it comes to English speaking.”(Teacher 4)

“However, mostly in the individual activities in terms of giving ideas, explaining or discussing something, maybe they could say something but not confident enough.”(Teacher 5)

The ongoing problem of inhibition, shyness, and low confidence levels in communicative situations and tasks was crucial as it would have an impact on students’ overall performance not only academically but also in their interaction with the people around them as Damanik (2018) also emphasized that language was used to communicate with other people as a means of expressing feelings and desires and understanding the world.

Building communication confidence was a complex process influenced by various factors, including individual personalities, the language environment at home, and the academic context. The excerpts revealed significant variance in confidence levels among students who were experiencing discomfort and anxiety when communicating in English, especially with strangers or outside of academic settings. Teachers' observations supported this, noting a substantial proportion of students displaying low confidence in their English communication skills. The key to improving confidence was creating supportive academic environments where students feel safe practicing and expressing themselves. Furthermore, recognizing and addressing the psychological barriers that students face, such as fear of embarrassment or making mistakes, was crucial. Strategic interventions, including more opportunities for speaking practice in less formal settings and fostering a positive feedback culture, could significantly bolster students' confidence. These findings were aligned with Burkard et al., (2005) and Hossain (2015), who signified that students tend to display a higher level of confidence if they were taught and exposed to transactional skills, such as negotiation, persuasion, and problem-solving. They further claimed that some students exhibited high levels of confidence, suggesting that improvements were attainable with appropriate support and intervention.

Vernacular Dependence. Using students mother tongue was apparent in discomfort with English, as students tended to resort to their vernacular language to express themselves. During the early years of education, students were exposed to English not only as a subject but also as a medium of instruction (Pangket, 2019). However, outside of school, students no longer practiced using English for transactional communication. The statements of the students corroborated this situation:

“At home, I only use Bisaya dialect, because that's what we're used to.”(Student 1)

“We communicate at home in vernacular language.” (Student 2)

“No, we're using our mother tongue which is Cebuano.”(Student 3)

“In my experience sir no, since the school is mostly speaking in Bisaya.”(Student 4)

“For me Sir, in our home we are using Bisaya or Cebuano.”(Student 5)

Inside the school, teacher also allows the students to use their vernacular language in expressing their ideas during communication. This was evident since not only students relied on using their mother tongue but as well as teachers allowed them to use it as a last resort just to fully emphasize the ideas that they had in mind. This was evident from the responses of the teachers themselves. Teachers 3 and 5 claimed:

“Sometimes, they are trying to construct it in Cebuano or in Filipino.”(Teacher 1)

“And then, mostly, they prefer to use vernacular.”(Teacher 2)

So, I give allowable adjustments by speaking in the local dialect or the vernacular or the Cebuano language, Cebuanong Dabao, in order to let them express themselves and answer the task correctly. (Teacher 3, Appendix M)

“They are trying their best to express it somehow, like in Filipino or in Bisaya.”(Teacher 4)

If they cannot express their ideas verbally, first I let them use the vernacular. (Teacher 5)

Generally, students employed different communication skills in various contexts they encountered. Most of them did not use the English language for transactional communication in real-life situations; instead, they utilized it primarily for academic purposes during classroom activities such as roleplays, simulations, and performance tasks. This observation was supported by Kolb and Kolb (2012), who noted that these activities aided in the development of students' communication skills proficiency. However, it was insufficient, as students still struggled in certain aspects, particularly oral communication proficiency (Pangket, 2019). The limited and selective use of the English language had an impact on students' proficiency, as they lacked practice in using the language in authentic situations.

Challenges Encountered by Senior High School Students in their Transactional Communication Skills

In academic settings, a "challenge" denotes a difficulty or obstacle encountered while striving for knowledge, conducting research, or pursuing academic objectives. Overcoming such challenges demands effort, skill, and strategic thinking. Challenges can also be an opportunity for growth and improvement. In this study, linguistic barriers, specifically grammar and vocabulary, were identified as a challenge. This also resulted in their discomfort in communicating in different contexts such as in academics and regular communication situations. The struggles in pronunciation was also evident among the students and mostly occurred with unfamiliar words and terminologies encountered. They had limited vocabulary as well as grammar knowledge added by the inability to pronounce words and terminologies properly, thus resulting in observed low confidence levels in transactional communication situations resulting in deficiency of communication practice.

Limited Grammar and Vocabulary. Linguistic problems specially in the aspect of grammar and vocabulary were notable on the responses of the senior high school students. Students are both aware of their problems in grammar and vocabulary as well as the importance of correcting it. They encounter problems in using correct punctuation marks, they encounter issues in following the subject-verb agreement in sentence constructions, and in the aspect of vocabulary they have difficulty in understanding and using different terminologies in different subjects specially if the terminologies were new to them thus reflecting the low vocabulary level of the students. These responses from the students were a clear manifestation of this problem in grammar and vocabulary phenomena:

“Yes, sir. I said earlier that I'm ashamed to talk to people because of my grammar. Limited? Yes, limited.”(Student 1)

“It affects my communication with others because people judge you when you don't have the right grammar in speaking and if they can't understand you.” (Student 2)

“Poor grammar or limited vocabulary can lead to misunderstanding it or difficulty expressing oneself clearly.”(Student 3)

“I cannot properly communicate because I'm conscious about, again, judgment because of my lack of knowledge in grammar and vocabulary.”(Student 4)

“Yes Sir. It's a really big effect especially in English. So should know the subject verb agreement.” (Student 5)

Even with the observed inhibition and low confidence levels of senior high school students, there were still students who tried their best to communicate transactionally using the English language. However, there were observable problems when it came to their grammar and vocabulary. The observation of the senior high school teachers in students' problems in grammar and vocabulary also confirmed that there were evident grammatical and vocabulary problems specifically when it comes to the proper use of subject-verb agreement and punctuation marks. Senior high school teachers said:

“Though they have their own point, they have their own ideas, however, when it comes to grammar and their correct pronunciation, they just change their answer and leave it to others to avoid such discrimination.” (Teacher 1)

“When it comes to vocabulary, they cannot find the right words to say.”(Teacher 2)

“They have poor vocabulary skills.” (Teacher 3)

“So, when we say the use of synonyms, the proper term, although the word is correct, needs to have the correct term to be used.” (Teacher 4)

“Number one that I observe is that they have poor vocabulary skills in building their vocabulary skills. Second, I observe that they have less knowledge when it comes to subject-verb agreement in improving their grammar, especially in writing..” (Teacher 5)

Moreover, discrimination was also observed by Teacher 1 in his class which was supported by his statement:

“When it comes to grammar and their correct pronunciation, they just change their answer and leave it to others to avoid such

discrimination”. (Teacher 1)

As a result, students tended to remain silent not only due to poor grammar and vocabulary but also because of psychological reasons or affective issues such as observed bullying, discrimination and fear of judgment which was also happening in typical classrooms (Derakhshan et al.,2016). These were affirmed by the statements from students 1, 2, and 4 who said:

There are people who are perfectionists when it comes to communication. So, when you talk to them in English language, it's embarrassing. Because they laugh at your grammar. Or your grammar is correct. (Student 1)

“I am not confident every time I do public speaking using the English language because I might get judged. So I’m nervous. (Student 2)

“Anxious, nervous because it's scary to make mistakes in what I'm saying, or I might be judged because of wrong grammar. (Student 4)

To support this, Gonzales (2023) identified specific discriminations that were experienced by students which were (1) judging, mocking, and laughing, (2) anxiety and fear, (3) exclusion, and (4) negative classroom environment; generally, students were discriminated due to low proficiency in English. These discriminations affected the student’s confidence and caused anxiety as well as hindered their language learning opportunities because they developed a fear of negative evaluation which affected their performance inside the classroom.

Language competence challenges presented a significant barrier to effective communication among senior high school students. These challenges encompass issues with vocabulary, grammar, and comprehension, all of which impact students' ability to express ideas clearly and confidently. Teachers identified a lack of practice and foundational language skills as key concerns, suggesting a need for the educational curriculum to address the practical application of English better. Pourmand et al., (2021) highlighted the importance of opportunities for practice in developing transactional skills among students. Additionally, the influence of the home language environment emerged as a crucial factor, with limited exposure to English outside academic requirements hindering proficiency. Addressing these challenges required a multifaceted approach, including increased engagement with the language in diverse contexts. This could involve integrating more interactive and communicative activities into the curriculum, promoting extensive reading beyond school hours, and utilizing technology to offer immersive language learning experiences. Such approaches aligned with Kolb and Kolb's (2012) integrated teaching approach, which combined traditional classroom instruction with experiential learning activities to enhance students' transactional skills. By bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical language competence, these strategies aimed to support students in overcoming language barriers and becoming more proficient communicators.

Pronunciation Struggle. Aside from grammar and vocabulary, problems in pronunciation as well were observed among senior high school students. The students mispronounced unfamiliar words or words that were new to them. These were the terminologies used in different subject areas specifically in their specializations which were mostly scientific terminologies and agricultural terminologies. Students revealed the following:

“Sometimes, it's like that. But, when it comes to reporting, I can't avoid it. There are... It's not just me. I would also see my classmates’ mispronouncing words.” (Student 1)

“Yes, I have mispronounced words.” (Student 2)

“Yes, sometimes I pronounce it the wrong way so it can affect my ability to communicate with others.”(Student 3)

“I mispronounce a word and then someone corrects me, I would take it, oh, okay, and then try again, not make the same mistake again.” (Student 4)

“Yes Sir, commonly you face unfamiliar words, and you don't know how to pronounce them.”(Student 5)

This situation was confirmed by the responses from their teachers who said:

“So sometimes their pronunciation is not used properly, the mispronunciation.”(Teacher 1)

“Oh, yes, sir. Like, they interchange the soft vowels, the pronunciation of vowel sounds becomes hard. Some of the consonants, like that, sir.” (Teacher 2)

“So, sometimes when there are disagreements about pronunciation between me and my students, we check on Google on how to pronounce it.”(Teacher 3)

“They have to be careful in the pronunciation of the vowels, like Yeah, like the pronunciation of I and E So, usually E is mispronounced as E.”(Teacher 4)

“There are times that they mispronounce some of the unfamiliar words. Most of these mispronounced words are unfamiliar words or new to them.”(Teacher 5)

Since the English language was not the first language of Filipinos, the longstanding problem of pronunciation was very evident as one of the challenges encountered by senior high school students considering that the Philippines was also composed of a variety of dialects. Depending on the place where they live and as well as their ethnic background, they also had different languages used which also influenced the pronunciation. This problem was also found in the study of Saavedra (2022) in which geographic location was a factor in the proper pronunciation of students. Tausug and Visayan speakers pronounced better words with voiceless dental fricatives compared to Chavacano. On the other hand, Chavacano pronounced better words with the sound voiced /th/ compared to the Tausug and Visayan speakers. These issues and challenges were found to be the major hindrance to senior high school students' effective transactional communication skills. It was also notable that senior high school teachers allowed students to use their vernacular language during classroom discussions and performance tasks.

This practice affirmed the findings of Koosha (2013) where teachers were also found to be one of the contributing factors that affected the transactional communication skills of students. Teachers had limited skills in handling communication activities and tasks which was needed hence Briggs (2014) emphasized the need for teachers to be well-equipped with skills in handling communication activities, especially in situations when students experience problems in using the language. They played a crucial role in facilitating this strategic learning by providing explanations, paraphrasing, and encouraging using native languages as a transitional tool. These strategies highlighted the interactive nature of language learning, where comprehension and communication were improved through active engagement rather than passive reception.

Overall, the linguistic and expression challenges, as well as the confidence level problems and basic language skills problems specifically the skill in pronunciation, were also greatly impacted by students' lack of practice in using the English language in transactional communication situations. This finding supported the earlier confirmation of students that their' transactional skills were not exercised and practiced regularly. The factors contributing to the development of transactional skills among students included exposure to real-life communication scenarios (Pourmand et al., 2021). This was evident since not only students relied on using their mother tongue but as well as teachers allowed them to use it as a last resort just to fully emphasize the ideas that they had in mind.

Finally, the responses from both senior high school students and senior high school teachers confirmed the actual existence of the mentioned issues and challenges in the student's transactional communication skills. Students' responses supported by their teachers' observations provided strong evidence that senior high school students transactional communication skills were not really coinciding with their current grade level and the expected communicative proficiency level on them. Thus, providing a negative risk to their future endeavors if left untreated.

Coping Mechanisms Senior High School Students Employ when they Encounter Issues and Challenges in their Transactional Communication Skills

This section offered the coping mechanisms employed by Grade 12 senior high school students when encountered with issues and challenges in their transactional communication skills. It contained the students' narratives on their experiences that confirmed the existence of these coping mechanisms. The coping mechanisms observed by the teachers were students stop talking or don't talk at all when engaged in transactional communication. Students practice self-regulation by relaxing themselves and trying to be calm. Students alongside being silent and not engaging in transactional communication, they also employ observations with the people and the communication situations happening around them, they are listening attentively and they ask assistance from their classmates and their teachers. Technological advancements were also contributing factors in students' coping mechanisms. Students used their cell phone's applications to help them with the transactional communication issues and challenges that they encounter.

When students felt uncomfortable with the communication, they found ways to end immediately the conversation or to avoid further communication problems, thus avoidance was identified. Observational coping was where students would just listen to the statements of the person they were communicating with. Meanwhile, when students are anxious, they self-regulate by trying to relax. The withdrawal was to initiate communicative activities and tended to find excuses and lastly, the escape by using technology to appear like they were preoccupied.

Conversation Termination. Every day, students were exposed to different communication situations where transactional communication skills were required. It could be inside the school environment, or outside public places. In situations where students were required to communicate with others and they felt uncomfortable, they tried to find ways or escape or to end the communication situation immediately. With the given issues and challenges experienced, they adopted coping mechanisms. Emerged coping mechanism when students feel anxious were found to be more of trying to avoid or escape when confronted by challenging situations that required their English transactional communication skills. SHS students revealed this feeling through their responses:

"I will end the conversation. I look for excuses. Like that, sir." (Student 1)

"If I'm not comfortable communicating with other people, I just limit my answers or sometimes I just don't speak."(Student 2)

"Sometimes I may pause, and I also gather my thoughts."(Student 3)

"I will try to excuse myself from the conversation and not engage again."(Student 4)

“Sometimes, commonly for me I am using my cellphone as an excuse and leave the uncomfortable zone.”(Student 5)

These coping mechanisms were contrary to what the Department of Education (DepEd) was trying to achieve in the quality of senior high school graduates who were expected to be masters of effective communication skills (DepEd Order No. 21, s.2019).

In relation to one of the identified issues and challenges of the senior high school students mentioned in the first part of this chapter which is the issue and challenge in social anxiety, teachers also observed this situation mainly in the teaching-learning process inside the classroom. Teachers observed that when students felt that they will be asked by the teacher to answer and participate in the tasks given to them, they try to look for excuses and they avoid engaging in the communication. There are students who tried but in the middle of the communication, they stop and sit. This problem was greatly impacted by their low self-confidence which was also one of the identified challenges encountered by the students and added by few other issues and challenges identified like problems in grammar and vocabulary as well as in pronunciation.

Aware of the issue in communication anxiety, teachers did not just let the students continue with the negative behavior. Teachers implemented strategies and techniques to address these problems. This was confirmed in the statements of teachers 1,3, and 5:

“But as a teacher, we need to remind them, so that's why we encourage them to be able to speak so that we know what we can do to help them.” (Teacher 1)

“I also taught them some strategies on how to present their products, but they really need to hone their communication skills, because in the 21st century, communication is really important.” (Teacher 3)

“Especially if I am having group activities, part of the rubric or the criteria is participation. So even though they have this problem or difficulty communicating, they still try their best to participate and cooperate with their group.”(Teacher 5)

Self-regulation. This coping mechanism had a connection to one of the identified issues and challenges which is something to do with students' confidence level when they are engaged in communication situations. When students are not confident with their communication skills, it affects their communication with other people and they tend to avoid participating in communication activities (Al Hosni, 2014). Inhibition and confidence relate to each other. With less confidence, their fear and anxiety to communicate inversely gets higher.

Moreover, as a result of having low self-confidence in communication situations, students stops talking and doesn't continue expressing their ideas and in worst case scenarios, they choose not to engage in any communication at all and keeps quiet. Students also practice self-regulation by being calm and trying to relax when situated in difficult transactional communication situations.

“I avoid intimidation but I stay calm.”(Student 1)

“What I do is just take a deep breath and repeat what I said earlier.”(Student 2)

“I practice deep breathing, positive self-talk and focus on the message rather than the nerves.”(Student 3)

“I address it by calming myself down and telling myself that it's going to be okay.”(Student 4)

“So, for me to address this a deep breath will do and think of it that after this it is a success.”(Student 5)

Observational Coping and Assistance Finding. In addition, in classroom discussions, when students are unable to express their ideas, they ask their classmates for the correct translation of the words, and they also ask their teachers how to properly translate and pronounce words. Teachers mentioned that for them to extract the answers of their students, they allow them to use vernacular language in expressing their ideas. As much as teachers wanted students to speak in the English language in transactional communication, they did not have a choice as it is their students coping mechanism, and if they would not allow the use of vernacular language, they could not do anything from the students except for those who were proficient students already, but those students who were proficient comprised only the small percentage of the population and still most number of students were not proficient and its quite notable that this was generally happening in the whole school and not only in certain grade levels. This situation inside the teaching-learning process in the classroom results in teachers allowing the students to use their mother tongue or vernacular language to emphasize their thoughts. The same factors affect students' communicative competence (Tuan and Mai, 2015).

In the regular teaching-learning process inside the classroom, senior high school teachers most of the time observed their students to ask for assistance when they had difficulty in expressing their ideas. This coincides with the earlier findings in relation to students' responses that they ask an assistance from their peers and teachers. They asked for assistance from their classmates or peers, but in cases when their classmates could not also help them, they were left with no option but to ask their teachers. The statement of Teacher 2 and 4 proved this situation:

“In my observation, when they are asked and then they cannot find the right words to say, they ask for assistance from the teacher, of course, from me, and sometimes they ask for help from their seat mates”. (Teacher 2)

“Others would also try to, um, perhaps, ask from their seatmates, like that, it's still a strategy while they are answering”. (Teacher 2)

“Usually, they ask the teacher and then the teacher will translate, the teacher will paraphrase, the teacher will um translate in Bisaya or in Tagalog the question”. (Teacher 4)

Moreover, the use of the mother tongue was allowed when students could not find any other means of expressing themselves in the language required for them to use. Most of the time, teachers’ instructions inside the classroom were generally in English language except for subjects Filipino, ESP, AP, and other related subjects. Because of students’ inability to both comprehend and communicate using the English language, teachers themselves allowed them to speak and communicate using their vernacular language which is Bisaya. Teachers wanted the students to learn but they were left without any option as allowing students to communicate in vernacular just to extract the knowledge and ideas from the students. Alongside this situation, the students felt shy and at the same time worried since they knew that in their grade level, it was expected for them to be proficient in using English transactional communication already, but the actual situation was different from what was expected.

These feelings of the students were also observed by the teachers during classroom discussions and activities. Students felt worried and teachers could observe in their facial expressions and gestures that they were confused and worried about what they were saying. Teachers 1 and 3 confirmed these observations through their statements:

Normally, since they have their own feelings also, they are affected, they are frustrated. However, they need to strive to overcome all their tasks. So, maybe one of the reasons is that they cannot avoid their worries, their downsides. (Teacher 1)

Students are really stressed if they are tasked to answer in English because they are not able to express themselves well. So, there's stress, it's intense. (Teacher 3)

Technological Assistance. Moreover, it is notable in the responses of the teachers that they confirm that one of the most common coping mechanisms of students, when faced with problems in transactional communication, includes the use of technology, particularly cellphones. The rise of smart devices and artificial intelligence (AI) provided both positive and negative effects, most especially in the field of education. Students used their devices as a form of excuse to escape communication situations and at the same time they have used it as a tool for them to enhance their transactional communication skills. Students mentioned about the specific mobile applications and social media platforms that they have used:

“Sir, apps like, for example, Quillbot.”(Student 1)

“Through reading, because when you read, you learn a lot of new words. I read online books.”(Student 2))

“I spend a lot of my time watching videos on social media, especially on YouTube or TikTok and Twitter.”(Student 4)

“There are apps in cell phones that I can use especially in making a grammar using English language.”(Student 5)

On the other hand, despite the negative effects of these advancements in technology, it still provided a positive impact on the learning of the students. This was observable in one of their coping mechanisms to address problems in grammar and vocabulary. Aside from using AI, some students used mobile applications and software to help them positively. Unlike AI, the mentioned applications and software did not make students reliant on the answers provided by the technology but rather used those applications as a means of improving their vocabulary and grammar.

Aside from the use of applications and software, students also mentioned watching movies and listening to music on different online platforms, which was also becoming a trend nowadays and helped them in their language learning. By reading the subtitles projected on the movies that they were watching, they also enriched their vocabulary. At the same time, through listening to music and memorizing its lyrics they were developing their grammar as well. The students also learned the correct pronunciation of different words. Student 1 confirmed this by saying:

“I have seen that they are more fluent in Korean because they are watching K-drama. So, if I want to be fluent in grammar and English, watching, sir, YouTube, movies, especially subtitles”. (Student 1)

Technology was pivotal in language learning, offering various resources and platforms that cater to diverse learning needs and styles. The excerpts show how students and teachers view and utilize technology as a significant part of the learning ecosystem. From using social media and digital content as informal learning tools to leveraging educational apps for structured learning, technology facilitates a more engaging and interactive approach to language acquisition.

However, it is also noted that technology can be a distraction or a means of avoiding communication challenges. To harness the full potential of technology in language learning, it is essential to integrate it thoughtfully into the curriculum, ensuring that it complements traditional learning methods rather than replacing them. This might involve curated selections of digital resources, guidance on effective online learning strategies, and training students in digital literacy to maximize their learning outcomes. Additionally, incorporating technology-based assignments encouraging active communication, such as creating videos or participating in online forums, can provide practical language use opportunities in a controlled, supportive environment. Ultimately, the goal is to create a balanced educational approach where technology enhances language learning without undermining the importance of face-to-face interactions and traditional learning methodologies, which reflects Ghavifekr & Rosdy's (2015) suggestion that incorporating technology and digital

resources into intervention programs can enhance students' engagement and facilitate the development of transactional skills.

Lastly, the senior high school teachers observed students' use of mobile devices, specifically mobile applications that helped them with grammar, vocabulary, and even pronunciation issues. This became also one of the coping mechanisms employed by students when faced with issues and challenges in transactional communication. Technology became an instrument or tool for them to help with their academic tasks. Teachers' 3 and 4 statements prove that students use their cellphones and browse the internet or use mobile applications and AI to help them with their transactional communication skills in the aspect of correct word pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary. Teachers 4 and 3 shared:

"Nowadays it's the use of the app in the cell phones, so students usually have their dictionaries in their cell phones and then the use of apps like Grammarly so they can type their thoughts there and then the app will translate". (Teacher 4)

"Because if they do not know how to answer the tasks or present themselves in English, they use Google Translate. They type in Tagalog in Google and then they translate it into English. So, that is why they can come up with a better output in English because of Google Translate. So, I said that the Gen Zs are really intellectual people, but they are global citizens because they are really dependent on apps and the internet. (Teacher 3)

The integration of technology in instructional activities and tasks was proven to be effective in developing transactional communication skills (Ghavifekr & Rosdy, 2015; Mulyadi et al., 2021). However, the Philippines has still a lot of issues to resolve considering the issues and challenges in the integration of technology in instructional pedagogy. These were the unavailability of technological resources and, the internet, intensified by teachers' insufficient knowledge of the new modalities used (Rudenko et al.,2020).

Overall, these issues and challenges alongside the coping mechanisms that senior high school students provided a clear picture of what was the current status of the transactional communication skills of senior high school students, especially in rural areas where there were limited resources used by teachers and students as well as limited exposure and practice were given in practicing students' English transactional communication skills. Hence, it was timely that intervention programs should be enhanced, refined, or created and implemented to help students develop not only their communication but also other important skills that they must possess when they graduate at the senior high school level.

Proposed Intervention Program to Address Identified Issues and Challenges in SHS Students Transactional Communication Skills

From both the responses of the senior high school students and the senior high school teachers observations, it was revealed that senior high school students in the locale experience issues and challenges when it comes to the their transactional communication skills. The identified issues and challenges must be given attention and must be addressed properly as neglecting these would impact the students' future employability since transactional communication skills were very important in the professional world (Lloyd-Walker et al., 2014).

After the identification of the issues and challenges and the coping mechanisms of senior high school students, several themes emerged that paved the way for the researchers crafting of the proposed intervention program. Table 3 showed the proposed intervention activities for the identified issues and challenges. These activities were the following: (1) transactional communication training, (2) building communication confidence, (3) strategic language learning, (4) grammar and vocabulary enhancement, and (5) pronunciation enhancement and technology technology integration training.

Table 3. *Proposed Intervention*

<i>Issues and Challenges</i>	<i>Coping Mechanisms</i>	<i>Intervention</i>
Communication Anxiety	Conversation Avoidance	Transactional Communication Training
Low Level of Confidence	Self-regulation	Building Communication confidence
Vernacular Dependence	Observational Coping	Strategic Language Learning
Limited Grammar and Vocabulary	Technology Assistance	Grammar and Vocabulary Enhancement
Pronunciation Struggles	Technology Assistance	Pronunciation Enhancement and Technology Integration Training

The following themes were already integrated and mentioned in the earlier discussion of this chapter. Nevertheless, these were considered in the researchers' crafting of the proposed intervention program to address issues and challenges in transactional communication skills. The intervention program proposal along with the action plan will be shown and discussed in the succeeding discussions. The intervention program proposal was crafted by the researcher considering the identified issues and challenges and the coping mechanisms identified in the earlier chapters of this study. Several considerations as well were made like the date and venue, source of fund, success indicators, and the steering committee.

The proposed intervention program which is entitled "Project Trans-Action: Navigating Interactional Nuances with Optimal Mastery". The overall matrix of this proposed intervention program is appended on this study (Appendix M). This proposed intervention program consisted of different tiers and each tier consisted of series of activities that would address the identified issues and challenges of the students. Activities were ordered starting from the basic going to the complex skills as the program was being executed. First, it would be focused on the grammar and vocabulary aspect, followed by building self confidence, addressing communication anxiety,

pronunciation struggles and lastly, activities that would be focused on integrating technology in developing students linguistic abilities. Technology was integrated and included in the program as it was notable coping mechanism of the students in addressing their encountered issues and challenges and it is very timely because of the advent of technology.

Tier 1 of the proposed intervention program is dedicated to the assessment and orientation. Students will be assessed on these following aspects: (1) grammar, (2) vocabulary, (3) pronunciation, and (4) confidence level in communication. Pre-assessment is needed as it will be the basis of the number of students that will be included in the intervention program. The assessment will be composed of simulations of different transactional communication scenarios just like a job interview, ordering goods, and communicating with native English speakers. Students will also be giving their own opinions, impromptu speaking, vocabulary check, and they will also be having their pen and paper test for the grammar aspect. Teachers will be using checklists also for the assessment of the students transactional communication skills. After the assessment phase, there will be an orientation for both the parents or guardians and the identified students that will be included in the program. This orientation will give the parents and the students the specificities of the intervention program.

Tier 2 of the proposed intervention program will be the conduct proper of the activities and strategies that will help the students improve their transactional communication skills. These activities will include the activities that would follow.

Grammar and Vocabulary Enhancement

To address language competence challenges specifically in the aspect of grammar and vocabulary, was the “word of the day”. Some English teachers were already implementing and practicing this strategy. But, as proposed, this intervention will be applied in all subject areas. Before the class starts, unfamiliar words would be presented, and this would be unlocked and will be used in sentence construction and integrated with experiential learning activities together with the supervision and assistance of the teacher. In this way, vocabulary and grammar enrichment would be secured. The consistent application and practice as well as the inclusion of experiential learning activities with the use of the target language helped improve the transactional communication skills of students (Kolb and Kolb, 2015). Students queries will also be encouraged and entertained to provide proper feedbacking and to allow positive communication between the students and the teachers.

Building Communication Confidence

Low self-confidence in transactional communication situations was one of the identified issues and challenges of senior high school students. Confidence was psychological and personal in a manner affected by a few factors such as level of proficiency and knowledge. Building the confidence of students would allow them to collaborate with others and participate in communicative tasks that would improve their skills. Collaboration was an essential skill, especially in workplaces that would be senior high school graduates’ path in the future. Moreover, Reciprocal Peer Teaching (RPT) was an effective way of building students’ confidence in communication and teamwork skills (Seenan et al.,2016). Allowing students to work with their peers would provide an environment that lessens anxiety and pressure. Hence, peer teaching would be adapted and integrated into the researcher’s proposed intervention.

Transactional Communication Training

In relation with the students high anxiety levels in engaging into various communication situations especially in transactional communication situations where English language is required, students will be trained on how to respond into different transactional communication situations. This intervention activity does not only focus on activities about development of transactional communication development but it encompass various activities including role-playing scenarios in which students act out different communication scenarios such as job interviews, customer service interactions, or peer discussions. This will provide practice for students in a safe environment and it will help them prepare for real-life situations. Another activity would be mock interviews in which mock interview sessions would be conducted with peers and teachers acting as interviewers. This will prepare students for job interviews and will reduce anxiety by familiarizing them with the format and common questions. Lastly, real-world exposure in which there will be invitation of guest speakers and video calls with professionals. This will expose students to real-world communication and reduces anxiety by familiarizing them with different settings.

Strategic Language Learning

The intervention will also strengthen strategic language learning. Strategic language learning involved employing specific tactics to overcome communication barriers, enhance understanding, and improve language proficiency. Students' strategies, such as active listening, simplifying language use, and asking for clarification, demonstrate their adaptability and willingness to engage in learning would be developed. Moreover, reading also stands out as a powerful tool in this strategic toolkit, for multiple purposes: expanding vocabulary, improving grammar understanding, and exposing learners to varied linguistic structures and cultural contexts. The students who actively use reading for self-improvement, recognize its role in broadening their lexical range and enhancing comprehension skills (Simamora and Oktaviani, 2020)

Teachers played a crucial role in facilitating this strategic learning by providing explanations, paraphrasing, and encouraging using native languages as a transitional tool. These strategies highlighted the interactive nature of language learning, where comprehension and communication were improved through active engagement rather than passive reception. Educational environments could

incorporate more structured opportunities for students to practice these tactics to support strategic language learning. This might include organized debates, peer teaching sessions, and language learning apps that allow for interactive learning. This result aligns with Ormrod's (2019) claim on the use of intervention programs that incorporate diverse teaching strategies, experiential learning activities, and technology-enhanced resources included in the multiple sources of learning and the need for adaptive learning environments. Encouraging a culture of curiosity, where questions were welcomed, and exploration were encouraged, can also foster a more strategic approach to language learning.

Pronunciation Enhancement and Technology Integration Training

To improve students pronunciation skills, several activities from (Emile Dodds, 2022) will be adapted in this intervention program. These activities involves the following: (1) minimal pairs, (2) tongue twisters, (3) fun with accents, (4) shadowing, (5) speed test, (6) hadars exercises, (7) word stress challenge, (8) master of pauses, (9) stressed out, (10) chunk it. In addition, the integration of technology in the teaching-learning process was undeniably a great help. The contribution of technologically enhanced materials in the motivation of learners thus leading to the development of communication skills (Mulyadi et al., 2021). Ghavifekr & Rosdy (2015) also posited that technology and digital resources incorporation in intervention programs enhanced students' engagement and learning of transactional communication skills. Thus, technological advancements specifically the mobile applications will be included in the proposed intervention program. These applications are useful in addressing their identified issues and challenges in transactional communication most especially in the aspect of grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation. These applications will be taught to students on how it will be properly used and how these applications would help them in their communication problems.

Tier 3 of the proposed intervention program will be dedicated to the final evaluation of the program. Evaluation is a crucial part in the overall effectiveness and success of the proposed intervention program. In this phase of the proposed intervention program, senior high school students transactional communication skills will be re-assessed and checked if there are improvements after the series of intervention activities that were given to them. This assessment phase will be composed of activities and tasks that would reveal their transactional communication skills level. This will also tell if the intervention program was effective on addressing the senior high schools students identified issues and challenges in their transactional communication skills based on the earlier findings of this study.

This intervention program was also patterned with the help of the Response to Intervention (RTI) Framework. This framework was generally used to identify and provide support to learners who were experiencing different struggles in various aspects of school. RTI was not a specific program or type of teaching but rather a proactive approach. This involved not only the teachers but also the school and the parents. This would allow students who are lagging far behind to catch up. Figure 1 showed the process flow of the RTI framework and its four (4) essential components: (1) universal screening, (2) progress monitoring, (3) multi-level prevention system, and (4) data-based decision making (Keeton, 2024).

Source: National Center on Response to Intervention, 2010

Figure 1. *Process Flow of RTI Framework*

The intervention program will start with the pre-assessment stage in which students' transactional communication skills will be assessed. There were still few students who were good and proficient in their transactional communication skills, hence a need to check who needed more help. Teacher 1 and Teacher 2 stated:

“Some of them are capable enough to report it in English. Then also their group members, they can also report also in English. However, some of the students are not that confident.” (Teacher 1)

“Mostly. Yes, mostly. Because there are still those who are good, especially those other students.” (Teacher 2)

After the pre-assessment stage and identification of students who had poor transactional communication skills, the intervention program will then proceed with the giving of intervention materials and tasks needed specifically for the identified issues and challenges of the students in their transactional communication skills. The intervention proper will be divided into different sessions and time to avoid interruption of regular classes inside the school. There will be sessions that will be integrated into the normal classroom discussion time and generally, most of the intervention activities will be utilizing “Catch Up Fridays”.

Catch Up Fridays was initiated by the Department of Education to address learning gaps and to prioritize holistic development among all elementary and secondary schools. This initiative was pronged with 2 approaches: (1) Drop Everything and Read (DEAR) which would promote reading and literacy, and (2) Inclusion of Values, Health, and Peace Education (DepEd MEMO No. 001, s. 2024).

Monitoring will be a crucial part of the intervention. The progress of students involved in the program would be assessed every quarter to ensure the development of their transactional communication skills. The multi-tiered prevention system comprises three tiers: primary, secondary, and intensive. These essential components were implemented throughout the school, with each tier providing a designated level of support tailored to a student's receptiveness to instructional materials.

At the primary prevention tier, emphasis was placed on delivering high-quality core instruction. The secondary tier targeted students identified as at risk for academic challenges, offering focused, supplementary instruction to small groups. The intensive intervention entailed personalized support for students demonstrating limited responsiveness to the primary or secondary prevention tiers.

One of the main goals generally in the implementation of various intervention programs to address varied issues and challenges is to assure that it will be an effective intervention program so that it would be beneficial not only to the students but to the general public as well. To achieve this goal, evaluating the effectiveness of the intervention program is necessary thus Kirkpatrick model will be adopted in evaluating the proposed intervention program. The Kirkpatrick Model is a widely used framework in assessing the effectiveness of different intervention and training programs. It comprised four tiers: (1) Reaction: This tier identifies the magnitude of participants' responses and contentment with the program., (2) Learning: Here, the focus is on evaluating how much new knowledge, skills, or attitudes participants have acquired due to the training, (3) Behavior: This tier scrutinizes any changes in behavior or level of performance following the training, (4)Results: This level measures the broader organizational outcomes or impacts of the training, such as enhanced productivity, cost reductions, or improved quality.

By employing the Kirkpatrick Model, institutions can evaluate the efficacy of their training and intervention programs and make well-informed decisions about future enhancements. This structured evaluation approach enables institutions to assess the impact of training across various levels, ranging from immediate reactions to long-term outcomes.

The effective implementation of intervention programs focused on transactional communication skills was crucial for developing holistic and academic success among students. Through interventions intended to address individual needs, such programs not only enhance students' communication abilities but also promote social, emotional, and academic growth, thereby equipping them with essential skills for thriving in diverse personal, educational, and professional settings.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, these were the implications:

The results provide empirical evidence that senior high school students transactional communication skills were being hampered by various issues and challenges, emphasizing the need to address the identified barriers. The findings of this study highlighted the complex challenges the senior high school students faced in developing effective transactional communication skills, underscoring the critical need for targeted interventions. The lack of communication confidence and language competence among students not only affected their academic performance but also impeded their ability to engage in meaningful social and professional interactions. These challenges necessitated a holistic approach to language education that addressed both the psychological and technical aspects of language learning.

Coping mechanisms employed by senior high school students imposed a negative approach and practice towards addressing identified communication proficiency problems and therefore might lead to decreasing communication proficiency levels among them if not addressed properly. Nonetheless, the coping strategies that were found, which ranged from using technology and home language contexts to strategic language acquisition, demonstrated the students' adaptability and resilience. These tactics demonstrated room for development and enhancement within the current language teaching framework. In particular, the thoughtful application of technology presented opportunities for creative language learning interventions that might meet students' varied requirements and learning preferences. Acknowledging and using these flexible tactics within official educational initiatives could greatly improve the effectiveness of language acquisition interventions, giving students the resources they require to get over obstacles to successful communication.

The significance of creating a systematic intervention program that capitalizes on students' abilities and tackles their difficulties with transactional communication skills could greatly increase students' confidence and competency in communication by creating an

environment that promotes practice, provides constructive criticism, and makes use of technology. Such interventions support students' personal development in addition to their academic and professional goals. The research provided insightful advice to curriculum designers, educators, and legislators who aimed to improve SHS students' communication abilities and eventually help learners succeed in a progressively interconnected and globalized world.

After a careful examination of the findings of the study, the following recommendations were formulated:

To the school principals, they may consider to ensure that communicative activities were clearly outlined in the daily lesson logs and diligently implemented during lesson delivery. This proactive approach will contribute to the effective enhancement of students' communicative skills within the educational setting. Emphasis should be placed on providing activities that would address each learners needs while integrating interactive resources and group tasks that will enhance student engagement and support.

To the English coordinators, they may implement a system for continuous evaluation and feedback, allowing for the intervention to be refined and adapted based on students' progress and feedback. This iterative process ensures that the intervention remains relevant and effective in meeting the evolving needs of the students.

To the language teachers, they may integrate technology into the language learning process to complement traditional methods. This could include language learning apps, online forums, and digital resources that promote interactive learning while minimizing distractions.

To the Department of Education-Curriculum and Teaching Committee, they may focus in professional development programs for teachers to ensure they are equipped with the latest pedagogical strategies for teaching transactional communication skills. This should include comprehensive training on fostering supportive and inclusive classroom environments that promote participation and alleviate anxiety among students.

To the language teachers, they may be trained in how to provide emotional and psychological intervention and support for learners with identified anxiety problems that affect their communication skills.

To the senior high school teachers of the school being studied, they may utilize the developed intervention program plan to enhance SHS students' transactional communication skills which was conceptualized based on their learners' capacities and needs.

To the future researchers, they may explore the effect of technological advancements on communicative proficiency of learners, especially in enhancing transactional communication skills.

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